

THE MAIN LEGAL ATTRIBUTES OF THE RIGHT TO A PERSONAL IMAGE

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Annotation. In the modern world, where images of people are widely used in the media, the Internet and other spheres, the right to personal image becomes especially relevant. The relevance of studying this topic is caused by the wide spread of images of people in modern society. With the development of technology, it has become easier than ever before to make, store and distribute photographs and video clips. The purpose of this article is to analyse the main legal features of the right to personal image, to identify its content and limits of implementation on the example of the legislation of Uzbekistan.

The article uses the methods of comparative legal analysis, system analysis, as well as the study of doctrinal sources and judicial practice. The results of the research can be used for further development of legal theory, as well as for improvement of legislation on personal data protection.

Keywords: Image, personal non-property rights, intangible goods, citizen's image, right to personal image, consent to use image.

The state provides legal protection and means of defence in respect of the most significant and important objects, tangible and intangible goods. In this regard, the image of a citizen is associated with such intangible benefits as personal inviolability, inviolability of private life, personal and family privacy, personal and family secrecy, dignity of a person, honour and good name, business reputation, authorship, and thus the right to it is subject to legal protection and defence.

In the textbook ‘Civil Law’ (general part) edited by Rakhmankulov H.R. in the chapter devoted to the regulation of intangible goods, including the right to image, it is noted that the identification of the nature of personal intangible goods is often very difficult due to the fact that there is a significant number of such objects, and their regulation due to their amorphous nature is mainly carried out by general legislative constructions, and their protection is the core of many normative legal acts in various spheres [1, p. 899].

Burkhanova L. in her work notes that intangible goods are characterised by a direct connection with the personality, which emphasises the uniqueness and inimitability of a person. The right to a name, the right of authorship, other personal non-property rights arise in a person by virtue of the law and are part of the content of legal capacity, that is, the ability to have civil rights and obligations is recognised for every citizen [2, p.25].

In connection with the popularisation of the use of social networks more and more often there are situations associated with unlawful behaviour of persons, which is expressed in the publication of images of citizens on accounts in social networks and other sites without their consent, because of which citizens appeal to the court to restore the violated right. It should be borne in mind that the satisfaction of claims depends on the evidence presented by the plaintiff. [3, p.254].

Talking about the legal attributes of an image, the researcher finds a number of uncertainties. Since the main problem is that the legislator has not fixed a specific definition and also a certain mechanism of legal regulation of relations arising in the process of using a personal image.

Thus, article 27 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that everyone has the right to freedom and personal inviolability. Which itself implies inviolability of personal image [4].

Article 99 of the Civil Code states that intangible goods include life and health, personal honour and dignity, personal inviolability, business reputation, inviolability of private life, private and family secrecy, the right to a name, the right to an image, the right of authorship, other personal non-property rights and other intangible goods belonging to a citizen by birth or by virtue of law, are not alienable or otherwise transferable [5]. There is no order of regulation of these rights in itself.

As a general rule, the publication and use of a citizen's image is possible only with his consent, and after his death with the consent of his children and surviving spouse, or in their absence, with the consent of his parents. The consent of a citizen to the publication and use of his/her image, including on the Internet, may be expressed orally, in writing, or in an explicit manner.

For example, in the legislation of Kazakhstan and Tajikistan, in addition to the general rule on the use of the image, the procedure for publicising, reproduction and dissemination of the image work is set out separately. The analysis of Article 145 of the Civil Code of Kazakhstan [6] and Article 176 of the Civil Code of Tajikistan [7] indicates that the key difference in the regime of these types of images is the definition of the circle of persons entitled to consent to the use of the image of a citizen after his death. As a general rule, such persons are recognised as heirs, and in respect of visual works - children and surviving spouse.

The legislation of Kyrgyzstan (Art. 19 of the Civil Code) [8] and Turkmenistan (Art. 17 of the Civil Code) [9] only states that no one has the right to publish and distribute a published image of any person without his consent. But it does not establish mechanisms for using the image of a citizen after his death.

Noteworthy is the position of Maleina M., who believes that, first of all, it is necessary to identify such a category as the individual appearance (appearance) of a citizen, which, as she believes, in a broad sense includes appearance, figure, physical

data, clothing, that is, the totality of such information about the person, which can be obtained without resorting to special research. And within this subjective right there is such a power as the right to dispose of one's image [10].

Malikov E. believes that the right to protect the image is closely intertwined with the norms of copyright, because, on the one hand, the author of a work of art (paintings, sculptures, photographs, etc.) has copyright, and on the other hand - they are limited by the will of the depicted person. Consequently, the author can realise his exclusive rights to a work of art only with the consent of the depicted person, except in cases provided for by law [11, p.39].

Since the legislation of Uzbekistan does not enshrine the limits of the right to image, we can refer to a more general interpretation of the limits of this right. For example, in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Personal Data' [12], it is defined that personal data is information recorded on electronic, paper and (or) other tangible media, relating to a certain individual or enabling its identification. Since the image of a person is directly related to such information, we can determine what the right to image includes based on this Law:

- the image of a person may be used only with the authorisation of the subject. (Art. 18);

- a person has the right to demand from any person to cease actions that violate his/her right to the image, as well as compensation for losses caused to him/her. (Art.30);

- consent may be withdrawn at any time. (Art. 30);

- consent to the use of an image may be given in any form that allows to confirm the fact of its receipt. (Art. 21).

Proceeding from the above, it is possible to identify the main legal features of

the image for further protection of the right to personal image:

- the image must be recognisable (the person in the image must be clearly visible enough to be recognisable);

- the image must convey the external appearance of the person (the image must be of the person who considers the image to be personal);

- the image must be made by the person or custom-made (if the person poses for a photograph or video at the request of another person, the image is not personal).

Based on the above, it is advisable to enshrine the main provisions of the right to an image in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Firstly, to include in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan an article on the right to an image and the conditions for the use of a citizen's image. To specify in what cases an image may be used without the consent of the citizen.

Secondly, it is necessary to enshrine in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan the right to an image not only as an intangible, but also as a good that constitutes a property component. In connection with global trends, where the image, voice and name of a citizen (in particular, celebrities) are often used for advertising purposes and other types of promotion of goods and services, it is necessary to legislate the conditions for concluding such transactions, to define the rights and obligations of the parties to such agreements.

Thirdly, to introduce the concept of citizen's image into the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Personal Data' and to define that personal data includes not only information about the subject, but also his image and voice.

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